

π -electron system of the phenyl ring, the overall -I inductive effect of the benzyl group is not significant as in the case of phenyl group, because the latter is directly attached to the nitrogen atom carrying a lone pair of electrons. Thus, the double bond character in case of these ligands would be higher than in the phenyldithiocarbamates and lower than in the dialkyldithiocarbamates.

Also, the (CN) bond order in the present dithiocarbamates is $\text{BzMeNCS}_2 > \text{BzEtNCS}_2 > \text{Bz}_2\text{NCS}_2 > \text{Bz-}i\text{PrNCS}_2 > \text{BzHNCS}_2$. The Bz group being common, the order can be explained on the basis of electronic effects of the other group, viz. H, Bz, Me, Et and *iso*-Pr. When H of the benzyldithiocarbamate is replaced by benzyl or alkyl group, the (CN) bond order is increased due to the electron donating tendency of the alkyl groups. If the electronic effects were purely inductive in nature, the (CN) bond order should increase as the size of the alkyl group increases. But in case of BzMedtc, BzEtdtc and Bz*iso*-Prdtc a reverse trend is observed i.e. the (CN) bond order decreases as we proceed from methyl to isopropyl through ethyl. In the dithiocarbamates, as the alkyl groups are attached to the partially double bond nitrogen, hyperconjugation is expected to be operative and the electron releasing ability can be in the order $\text{Me} > \text{Et} > \textit{iso}\text{-Pr}$. The position of Bz₂dtc can similarly be explained. However, kinematic effects due to increasing mass of the alkyl group have also been suggested to be responsible^{5,6}.

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Stability Constants of Fe(II), Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II) and Cd(II) Complexes of 2, 2'-Dipyridyl-2-Pyrimidylhydrazone

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2, 2'-Dipyridyl-2-pyrimidylhydrazone (DPPmH) was employed by Singh¹ for spectrophotometric determination of various transition metals. In

this paper the stepwise stability constants of binary complexes of DPPmH at pH 9.0 are reported. At pH 9.0 these metals are simultaneously determinable^{2,3} and hence pH 9.0 is selected for present studies. The Yatsimirskii's^{4,5} and Leden's⁶ graphical extrapolation methods were applied with necessary modification⁷ to calculate the values of stepwise stability constants. The experiments were performed at constant temperature $30 \pm 1^\circ$.

Experimental

2, 2'-Dipyridyl-2-pyrimidylhydrazone (DPPmH) was prepared as described earlier¹. 0.002M reagent solution in 40% ethanol-water was used. Solutions of Fe(II), Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II) and Cd(II) were prepared and standardised as reported in earlier communications^{2,3}. 1.0% Ascorbic acid in distilled water was used to prevent oxidation of Fe(II).

Apparatus: Beckman model DU 2 spectrophotometer with quartz cells of 10 mm light path was used for all photometric measurements. An ELICO pH-meter with glass and saturated calomel electrodes was employed for pH adjustments. All measurements were made at $30 \pm 1^\circ$ using thermostat.

Procedure: A solution containing a known quantity of metal ion [$\text{Fe(II)} = 3.0 \times 10^{-5} M$; $\text{Co(II)} = 2.0 \times 10^{-5} M$; $\text{Ni(II)} = 8.0 \times 10^{-6} M$; $\text{Cu(II)} = 1.0 \times 10^{-5} M$ and $\text{Cd(II)} = 7.5 \times 10^{-6} M$] varying quantity of DPPmH solution and 2 ml 1% ascorbic acid was adjusted to pH 9.0 in 40% ethanol-water, total volume being 25 ml. The absorbances were noted at respective wavelengths of maximum absorption [580, 460, 430 and 440 nm for Fe(II), Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II) and Cd(II), respectively] against the reagent as a blank. The concentration of complex formed was computed from the appropriate calibration curve.

TABLE I—STABILITY CONSTANTS FOR DPPmH COMPLEXES AT pH 9.0

	Yatsimirskii's method	Leden's method	Mole ratio method
Fe(II)-DPPmH			
log K_1	5.34	5.08	—
log K_2	4.95	4.40	—
log β_2	10.29	9.48	10.13
Co(II)-DPPmH			
log K_1	4.79	4.78	—
log K_2	4.52	4.52	—
log β_2	9.31	9.30	9.84
Ni(II)-DPPmH			
log K_1	5.67	5.70	—
log K_2	5.40	5.45	—
log β_2	11.07	11.15	11.61
Cu(II)-DPPmH			
log K_1	5.25	5.16	—
log K_2	4.97	4.97	—
log β_2	10.22	10.13	10.88
Cd(II)-DPPmH			
log K_1	6.26	6.30	—
log K_2	5.97	6.05	—
log β_2	12.23	12.35	12.30

Results and Discussion

The stoichiometric studies⁸⁻¹⁰ revealed that the complexes are binary [1 : 2, M : L] in nature.

Stability constants : The metal-ligand stepwise stability constants at pH 9.0 of these complexes were computed from the spectrophotometric data by Yatsimirskii's^{4,5} and Leden's⁶ methods in modified forms⁷.

The equilibrium constants thus obtained are reported in Table 1.

It is seen from Table 1 that the overall stability constants by these three methods agree with each other.

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Selectivity of Heterogeneous Ion-Exchange Membrane Discs with Reference to their Water Content, Porosity, Swelling, Electrolyte Absorption and Electrical Conductance

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IN heterogeneous membranes, the effect of binder cannot be ignored and so the study of some basic properties of the membrane becomes necessary. Michaelis¹ was the first to establish the standard electrochemical criteria for membrane characterisation, i.e., water content, porosity, swelling, electrolyte absorption and electrical conductivity.

Later Gregor^{2,3}, Wyllie⁴ and Hale⁵ reported on the characterisation of heterogeneous ion selective membranes. Recently, we have used the heterogeneous membranes of pyridinium molybdoarsenate⁶ (PMA) and rubidium⁷ and copper(II)⁸ tungstoarsenates (RbWA and CuWA) as ion selective electrodes. Present communication reports on the basic characteristics and its relationship with electrochemical performance of these heterogeneous ion exchanger membrane discs.

Experimental

Reagents and materials : All the reagents used were of analytical grade. Respective compounds, i.e., PMA, RbWA and CuWA and their heterogeneous membranes in Araldite were prepared as reported earlier⁶⁻⁹. Observations were made with two membranes of each exchanger.

Water content, porosity, swelling and electrolyte absorption^{2,5} : The membrane was kept immersed in a solution of 1 mol dm⁻³ NaCl for 24 hr to attain equilibrium. It was then taken out and the adhering electrolyte was wiped out. The thickness of this swollen membrane and its difference with that of dry membrane was taken as swelling. [An average value of the thicknesses measured carefully at different points of the membrane with a screw gauge (l.c.=0.001 cm) was taken as the thickness of the membrane]. The membrane was then washed several times with conductivity water and dried in a vacuum desiccator. The washings were collected to measure electrolyte absorption, conductometrically. The dried membrane was weighed to a constant weight and the difference in this weight (Ww) and the weight (Wd) of the membrane before immersing in the electrolyte solution divided by Ww was taken as water content. The porosity¹⁰ (ϵ) was calculated from the relationship,

$$\epsilon = \frac{Ww - Wd}{A.L. \rho w}$$

where A=area of the membrane, L=thickness of the membrane and ρw =density of water.

Conductance : The method recommended by Lakshminarayanaiah¹¹ was used for the determination of conductance of the membranes. The membrane was cemented between two half cells with the help of Araldite. It was then equilibrated by filling the half cells with 0.1 mol dm⁻³ NaCl solution. The solution was then replaced by mercury. The conductance was measured by connecting the Pt electrodes to the conductivity bridge.

Results and Discussion

When a heterogeneous membrane is immersed in water or electrolyte solution, water or solution may penetrate into the membrane structure occupying interstices which are present or which develop as a result of the difference between the swelling of